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Structural and functional characterization of proteins
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ABSTRACT

Poster session

ENGINEERED HYDROPHOBIN–LACCASE CHIMERAS FOR ENHANCED ENZYMATIC FUNCTIONALIZATION OF CELLULOSE IN ACTIVE PACKAGING

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The increasing demand for sustainable alternatives to petroleum-based plastics has driven growing interest in cellulose as a renewable and biodegradable material for food packaging. However, its intrinsic hydrophilicity limits its direct application, making surface functionalization strategies essential to improve its performance [1]. Within the PRIMA project MATE4MEAT, phenolic compounds were recovered from agro-industrial by-products—such as olive pomace, spent coffee grounds, and citrus peels—via microwave-assisted extraction and used as substrates for enzymatic cellulose modification.

In this study, an eco-friendly functionalization approach based on laccase-catalyzed grafting was developed to tailor cellulose surface properties. The native laccase POXA1b from *Pleurotus ostreatus* [2] and its engineered chimeric variant Vmh2–POXA1b [3], obtained by fusion with a hydrophobin, were employed. The laccase catalyzes the oxidation of phenolic compounds, generating reactive radicals able to covalently bind to cellulose, ensuring stable surface modification. The chimeric enzyme combines the catalytic activity of POXA1b with the self-assembling and adhesive properties of the hydrophobin Vmh2, enhancing enzyme anchoring and improving substrate interaction.

This strategy enabled the development of functionalized cellulose materials with hydrophobic and antioxidant properties, demonstrating the potential of enzyme engineering for active food packaging applications. This approach offers a sustainable route to tailor material functionality under mild conditions while valorizing agro-industrial by-products. Moreover, the versatility of the enzymatic system allows effective interaction with different phenolic biomasses, promoting the development of innovative and eco-friendly packaging solutions.

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